

Funded by
the European Union

Ref: Ares(2025)4276416 - 27/05/2025

PROSPLIGN

Prospecting natural lignin biodiversity towards unlocking value-added bioactive motifs and molecules

The PROSPLIGN project has received funding from the Horizon Europe Programme of the European Union under Grant Agreement n° 101135298.

WP7

Magfi

D7.5 – Intermediate Policy Brief

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	101135298	Acronym	PROSPLIGN	
Full Title	Prospecting natural lignin biodiversity towards unlocking value-added bioactive motifs and molecules.			
Start Date	01/01/2024	End Date	31/12/2026	
Project Website	prosplign.eu			
Deliverable	D7.5 – Intermediate Policy Brief			
Work Package	WP7 – Dissemination, exploitation, and communication			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31/05/2025	Actual	27/05/2025
Type	R – Document, report	Dissemination Level		PU - Public
Lead Beneficiary	MAGFI			
Responsible Author	Zoi Volioti (MAGFI)			
Contributions from	Camille Mallat (MAGFI), Malachi Gillick-Healy (KELADA)			

Funded by the European Union. **Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s)** only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

DISCLAIMER: Please note that this PUBLIC deliverable has been reviewed by members of the PROSPLIGN DCE Committee, for the purpose of minimising the risks of potential disclosures that may negatively affect the exploitability of relevant project KERs. While the DCE committee advice does not constitute legal advice, and the content of any deliverable is of exclusive competence and responsibility of the partner in charge of the same, the content of this PUBLIC deliverable may have been adapted by the deliverable owner considering the advice of the PROSPLIGN DCE Committee. Further data might be made available to the scientific community and general public at later stage of the project, subject to relevant DCE and IPR strategy validation and progresses.

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Description	Contributor
0.1	17.11.2024	Table of contents draft	Zoi Volioti (MAGFI)
0.2	14.04.2025	First draft sent for internal review	Zoi Volioti (MAGFI)
0.3	05.05.2025	Final draft sent for internal review - Comments and edits incorporated from the management team	Vanessa Spadaro, Camille Mallat, Zoi Volioti, Filippo Giancarlo Martinelli (MAGFI)
0.4	09.05.2025	Deliverable sent to partners for approval/edits	Zoi Volioti (MAGFI)
0.6	16.05.2025	Comments and edits incorporated from the Consortium partners	Zoi Volioti (MAGFI); Malachi Gillick-Healy (KELADA); Elina Roine (UH)
0.7	26.05.2025	Final deliverable version sent to COO to submit it to the portal	Zoi Volioti (MAGFI)
0.8	27.05.2025	Final check by COO as part of the DCE Committee review task and submission	Arlene Bonner (KELADA)

List of Participants

#	Participant (organisation name)	Acronym	Country	EU	Type
1	KelAda Pharmachem	KELADA	Ireland	Yes	SME
2	University of Helsinki	UH	Finland	Yes	UNI
3	Fundación Medina	MEDINA	Spain	Yes	RPO
4	NOVA University of Lisbon	NOVA	Portugal	Yes	UNI
5	University College Dublin	UCD	Ireland	Yes	UNI
6	Magfi ltd	MAGFI	Malta	Yes	SME
7	Bern University of Applied Sciences	BFH	Switzerland	No	UNI

TABLE OF CONTENTS

List of Participants	2
1 Introduction	4
2 The key policy and legislative framework governing PROSPLIGN’s primary feedstock	5
2.1 THE CONVENTION ON BIOLOGICAL DIVERSITY	5
2.2 THE NAGOYA PROTOCOL	6
2.3 EU REGULATION NO 511/2014	7
3 Intermediate PROSPLIGN policy recommendations	9
3.1 RECOMMENDATION #1: CLOSING THE UNDERSTANDING GAP BETWEEN EU POLICY BRIEFING AND EU-FUNDED RESEARCH	10
3.2 RECOMMENDATION #2: INCORPORATING SPECIFIC POLICY IMPLEMENTATION MEASURES INTO THE NEXT CALL FOR PROPOSALS	11
3.3 RECOMMENDATION #3: CREATING A CERTIFICATION TO STANDARDIZE THE CHARACTERIZATION AND LIGNIN BIOPROSPECTING VALORISATION TO IDENTIFY BIOACTIVE MOLECULES	11
4 Concluding remarks	13
5 Annex.....	14
5.1 POLICIES AND REGULATIONS MENTIONED IN THE PROSPLIGN PROJECT’S DESCRIPTION OF ACTION (DOA).....	14
5.2 POLICIES AND REGULATIONS POTENTIALLY APPLICABLE TO THE PROJECT AS A WHOLE AND RELATED TO THE IDENTIFIED KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	17

1 Introduction

The **PROSPLIGN** project - **PROSP**ecting natural **LIGN**in biodiversity towards unlocking value-added bioactive motifs and molecules - is a **European funded Research and Innovation Action** project. Our **key objective** is to apply state-of-the-art methodologies to prospect the bioactivity potential of lignin, a **natural, abundant and sustainable source material**. Our **mission** is to **discover new bioactive chemicals** derived from lignin and to **validate their potential** for application in the pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and fragrances markets.

Following a legislation and policy background research, an **internal consortium discussion**, as well as three designated **working sessions with our “sister project” [BRYOMOLECULES](https://bryomolecules.eu/)**¹ on how to approach this intermediate policy brief deliverable, the PROSPLIGN partners, with the integral guidance of our REA Project Officer, have reached a unanimous decision to focus on policy recommendations that surround the project’s call topic of “**biodiversity**”.

On this account, D7.5 outlines the context of the “**Convention on Biological Diversity**” as well as the “**Nagoya Protocol**” and the **EU REGULATION (EU) No 511/2014 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL** of 16 April 2014 on “*compliance measures for users from the Nagoya Protocol on **Access to Genetic Resources** and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization in the Union*”.

- It is noted here that this public report does not constitute a joint policy brief for the two projects. Despite the fact that the two projects fall under the same HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions call topic ‘[HORIZON-CL6-2023-CIRC BIO-01: Land-based bioprospecting and production of bioactive compounds and functional materials for multiple bio-based value chains](#)’, with the Granting Authority being the same for both projects, the [European Research Executive Agency](#), the natural feedstock that is valorised and bioprospected is different for the two projects and, based on the insofar achieved results, the observed convergence does not in our views justify the establishment of a joint policy brief. That noted, the two consortia have agreed to tentatively work together on a White Paper on biodiversity, beyond their official deliverables duties, in order to continue their close collaboration.

Having said this, this report offers an insight on how lignin – the natural resource that the PROSPLIGN project utilises as feedstock – **ties in with the preservation of the European biodiversity and offers a set of tailored to the project scope recommendations**.

¹ <https://bryomolecules.eu/> - accessed 13th May 2025

2 The key policy and legislative framework governing PROSPLIGN's primary feedstock

The following sections describe in brief the political and legal framework that governs the scope of PROSPLIGN's primary feedstock - natural lignin – in order to tie the section that follows and covers the recommendations outlined based on the insofar research and discussions within the consortium. These included discussions between the Coordinator (KELADA), the DCE Manager (MAGFI) and other consortium partners also including within the second General Assembly meeting of the consortium, which took place in Lisbon in January 2025, as well as further working sessions organised with the PROSPLIGN sister project BRYOMOLECULES to seek potential synergies and a joint policy brief.

2.1 The Convention on Biological Diversity

The [Convention on Biological Diversity \(CBD\)](https://www.cbd.int/)² is the international legal instrument for "the conservation of biological diversity, the sustainable use of its components and the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of the utilization of genetic resources" that has been ratified by 196 nations including all EU member states as the Convention is ratified by the European Union itself and each EU member state³.

Its overall objective is to encourage actions, which will lead to a sustainable future. The conservation of biodiversity is a common concern of humankind. The Convention on Biological Diversity covers biodiversity at all levels: ecosystems, species and genetic resources. It also covers biotechnology, including through the [Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety](https://bch.cbd.int/protocol)⁴. In fact, it covers all possible domains that are directly or indirectly related to biodiversity and its role in development, ranging from science, politics and education to agriculture, business, culture and much more.

² <https://www.cbd.int/>

³ <https://www.cbd.int/information/parties.shtml>

⁴ <https://bch.cbd.int/protocol>

2.2 The Nagoya Protocol

The [Nagoya Protocol](#)⁵ is a protocol to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), first signed by world leaders in 2010. The European Union is a party to the CBD, together with 193 countries. The protocol aims to share out the benefits of using genetic resources in a fair and equitable way.

The decision to sign it officially approves the ‘Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity’ on behalf of the European Union (EU). Through this approval, the EU has become legally bound to the protocol, which is an important agreement on the international governance of biodiversity. The Nagoya Protocol implements the third aim of the CBD, access and benefit sharing (ABS), which focuses on the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising from the use of genetic resources, including by appropriate access to genetic resources and appropriate transfer of relevant technologies. Genetic resources are genetic materials of actual or potential value, from natural or cultivated stocks (e.g. seed banks or botanical gardens). These resources are typically used by a wide range of sectors in nature-based research and development as a basis for innovation, such as for new medicines, chemicals or cosmetics.

The CBD recognises countries’ sovereign rights over their natural resources. ABS in the context of the Nagoya Protocol is based on this principle. Parties to the protocol have the authority to decide whether they wish to regulate access to their genetic resources and set out conditions for the sharing of benefits (e.g. through rules and procedures for prior informed consent and the negotiations of mutually agreed terms with the user of genetic resources).

The Nagoya Protocol also applies to the use of traditional knowledge associated with genetic resources held by indigenous peoples and local communities. The protocol **sets out mandatory rules on compliance for all parties**, in order to monitor the use of genetic resources once they leave the provider country. The protocol will create greater legal certainty and transparency for both providers and users of genetic resources, whilst promoting benefit-sharing. The benefits generated and shared under the guidance of the protocol should contribute to support the conservation of biological diversity and the sustainable use of its components (the first and second aims of the CBD).

⁵ <https://www.cbd.int/abs>

2.3 EU REGULATION No 511/2014

This [EU Regulation⁶](#) establishes **rules governing compliance with access and benefit-sharing for genetic resources and traditional knowledge associated with genetic resources** in accordance with the provisions of the Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity (the ‘Nagoya Protocol’). The effective implementation of this Regulation will also contribute to the conservation of biological diversity and the sustainable use of its components, in accordance with the provisions of the Convention on Biological Diversity (the ‘Convention’).

Based on **Article 3 of the Regulation** and for the specific purpose, **the definitions** of the Convention and the Nagoya Protocol as well as the following definitions **apply**:

- (1) *‘genetic material’ means any material of plant, animal, microbial or other origin containing functional units of heredity;*
- (2) *‘genetic resources’ means genetic material of actual or potential value;*
- (3) *‘access’ means the acquisition of genetic resources or of traditional knowledge associated with genetic resources in a Party to the Nagoya Protocol;*
- (4) *‘user’ means a natural or legal person that utilises genetic resources or traditional knowledge associated with genetic resources;*
- (5) *‘utilisation of genetic resources’ means to conduct research and development on the genetic and/or biochemical composition of genetic resources, including through the application of biotechnology as defined in Article 2 of the Convention;⁷*

⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2014/511/oj/eng>

⁷ **Important note:** based on the input by the PROSPLIGN coordinator KELADA, *‘R&D on biochemical composition of genetic resources’ nominally describe our PROSPLIGN depolymerisation of lignin’*. Based on the input from the Helsinki University team the term that applies to the lignin used in the PROSPLIGN project is that the samples the project valorises are a ‘derivative’ which means a naturally occurring biochemical compound resulting from the genetic expression or metabolism of biological or genetic resources, even if it does not contain functional units of heredity,

- (6) *‘mutually agreed terms’ means the contractual arrangements concluded between a provider of genetic resources, or of traditional knowledge associated with genetic resources, and a user, that set out specific conditions for the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the utilisation of genetic resources or of traditional knowledge associated with genetic resources, and that may also include further conditions and terms for such utilisation as well as subsequent applications and commercialisation;*
- (7) *‘traditional knowledge associated with genetic resources’ means traditional knowledge held by an indigenous or local community that is relevant for the utilisation of genetic resources and that is as such described in the mutually agreed terms applying to the utilisation of genetic resources;*
- (8) *‘illegally accessed genetic resources’ means genetic resources and traditional knowledge associated with genetic resources which were not accessed in accordance with the national access and benefit-sharing legislation or regulatory requirements of the provider country that is a Party to the Nagoya Protocol requiring prior informed consent;*
- (9) *‘collection’ means a set of collected samples of genetic resources and related information that is accumulated and stored, whether held by public or private entities;*
- (10) *‘association of users’ means an organisation, established in accordance with the requirements of the Member State in which it is located, that represents the interests of users and that is involved in developing and overseeing the best practices referred to in Article 8 of this Regulation;*
- (11) *‘internationally recognised certificate of compliance’ means a permit or its equivalent issued at the time of access as evidence that the genetic resource it covers has been accessed in accordance with the decision to grant prior informed consent, and that mutually agreed terms have been established for the user and the utilisation specified therein by a competent authority in accordance with Article 6(3)(e) and Article 13(2) of the Nagoya Protocol, that is made available to the Access and Benefit-sharing Clearing House established under Article 14(1) of that Protocol.*
-

3 Intermediate PROSPLIGN policy recommendations

Based on the definitions provided in the previous section, **lignin derived bioactive molecules may be perceived in this context as “utilisation of genetic resources”** as it when derived from some of the technologies applied by PROSPLIGN it might constitute a plant extract with a biochemical composition worth conducting research upon and utilisation of.⁸

*‘Lignin is an organic substance binding the cells, fibres and vessels which constitute wood and the lignified elements of plants, as in straw. After cellulose, it is the most abundant renewable carbon source on Earth. Between 40 and 50 million tons per annum are produced worldwide as a mostly non-commercialized waste product. It is not possible to define the precise structure of lignin as a chemical molecule. Lignin is commonly defined as **a dendritic cross-linked biopolymer of consisting of phenylpropanoid basic units, and whose specific chemical composition varies according to the plant species.***

There are many novel & early stage lignin extraction methods, however the two principal categories of industrially produced lignin are: those which are sulphur bearing and those which are sulphur-free. It is the sulphur bearing lignins which have to date been commercialized. These include lignosulphonates (world annual production of 500,000 tons) and Kraft lignins (under 100,000 tons p.a.). Due to the lack of suitable industrial processes, the sulphur-free lignins are as yet non-commercialized.’⁹

As a natural and renewable raw material, obtainable at an affordable cost, lignin’s substitution potential extends to any products currently sourced from petrochemical substances and therefore its research and valorisation makes for a great opportunity to tap into nature’s ‘hidden gems’, uncover their potential uses **while adhering to the preservation of the unique European biodiversity and its governing regulations**. While the call topic that the PROSPLIGN project answers to, specifically mentions ‘*the need to guarantee biodiversity preservation and compliance with relevant international rules on access to biological resources, their sustainable*

⁸ On utilisation: this definition is quite broad and covers various activities relevant for many sectors, without providing for a list of specific activities to be covered. Such lists were considered during negotiations on the Nagoya Protocol but were not included in the end, so as not to pre-empt changes in the rapidly evolving knowledge and technology in this domain. (Guidance document on the scope of application and core obligations of Regulation (EU) No 511/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the compliance measures for users from the Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilisation in the Union 2021/C 13/01 - https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.C_.2021.013.01.0001.01.ENG&toc=OJ%3AC%3A2021%3A013%3ATOC)

⁹ The lignin definition outlined in detail here at the International Lignin Institute website: <https://www.ili-lignin.com/what-is-lignin.html>

use and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits from their utilisation, with the national regulations in the source countries and with the Convention on Biological Diversity and its Nagoya Protocol', numerous discussions between the COO and the MAGFI team took place to define the recommendations that would best benefit the knowledge of both the REA policy officers and consequently the ['Expert group on Access and benefit sharing \(ABS\) under the Nagoya Protocol \(E03123\)](#)¹⁰ in DG Environment as well as the [ABS Consultation Forum members](#).¹¹

3.1 Recommendation #1: Closing the understanding gap between EU policy briefing and EU-funded research

As a first step towards the development of this policy brief deliverable, the MAGFI team listed the policies and legal documents that bind both the more general project scope as well as selected Key Exploitable Results. The second step in activity was to consult the Project Officer during the project's second General Assembly (21-22 January 2025, Lisbon, Portugal) and discuss with her the possible outline of the deliverable in order to ensure its best use. The Project Officer provided additional valuable explanations to the consortium members on **'how'** specifically a Research and Innovation Action policy brief could look like and **'what'** are the topics that could be outlined in it to guide policy makers in the betterment of the implementation of the Nagoya Protocol and other relevant policies in Europe.

Following the discussion with the Project Officer, the PROSPLIGN consortium as a whole, has now a very clear understanding of the Funding Body latest preferences for the format and content of a RIA policy brief. The Magfi team shared the obtained knowledge with its "sister project" BRYOMOLECULES in a dedicated working session in an effort to also exchange mutual learnings from the other project at the same time. The working session and the face-to-face PROSPLIGN discussion with the Project Officer, revealed that, despite the fact that knowledge on what a policy brief is somehow available and can be processed, **the specific assistance of the funding and policy bodies is of particular benefit.**

It is therefore recommended that the European Commission and REA intensify their actions towards sharing the knowledge a policy brief can play in the intersection of funding primary research and its actual policy betterment. While it is very much understood that the RIA policy

¹⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?lang=en&groupId=3123&fromMeetings=true&meetingId=29214>

¹¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?lang=en&groupId=3396>

briefs can constitute a great tool for ongoing discussions among the consortia partners, **a set of more guided communications tools or a dedicated webinar on what essentially policy making in the EU means and more specifically what a RIA policy brief should focus on**, would be very much welcomed by the next project beneficiaries and assist the future policy makers too in identifying the true gaps in policy making and implementation.

3.2 Recommendation #2: Incorporating specific policy implementation measures into the next call for proposals

In the spirit of the previous recommendation on a clearer communication of what a specific Research and Innovation Action (RIA) policy brief could constitute of, **the same clearer definition could apply in the next call for proposals with an additional and more detailed description in the objectives sections on the call**. While the PROSPLIGN consortium researched the policies mentioned in the call and added in the proposal narrative how the research and its results contribute to the preservation of the European Biodiversity and the European Bioeconomy Strategy, a more thorough study of the policies and legal framework was required during the project to understand fully where the project – and the project feedstock (lignin) and research methods fit the Nagoya Protocol implementation.

Project proposals need to list and study ahead of their acceptance existing and similar to their scope national, European and international funded projects and initiatives. An exercise for example on studying the policy, policies and legislation that adhere to the project call **would put into force a ‘push’ for extended study and knowledge of what European Policy making means** and how basic research can meet the European Union’s objectives and targets.

Taking also into consideration the fact that for both projects (PROSPLIGN and BRYOMOLECULES) the intermediate and final policy brief deliverables were an additional request from the funding body during the Grant Agreement Preparation stage, it is becoming more and more important that the call for proposals need to include indications - if not an example - on what specific ‘policy item’ the project may be encouraged focus and contribute during its implementation. This would also allow the involved partners to better budget for such activity at proposal preparation stage.

3.3 Recommendation #3: Creating a certification to standardize the characterization and lignin bioprospecting valorisation to identify bioactive molecules

While studying the Nagoya Protocol and its implementation in the lignin market, the Magfi team came across a company that states its product is ‘Nagoya Compliant’ and researched the way a lignin product could be checked for compliance with the Nagoya Protocol.

While the Magfi study revealed that there is a Guidance Document¹² from the European Commission, a Code of Conduct for Best Practice for access and Benefit sharing from the Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities (CETAF)¹³ as well as ISO¹⁴ standards related to commitment to quality, safety, efficiency, and continuous improvement across various industries, including IT, biotechnology, aerospace, manufacturing, and retail, such as [ISO 9001¹⁵](#), [ISO 14001¹⁶](#), and [ISO 45001¹⁷](#) that provide a more general framework that enhances customer satisfaction, operational efficiency, and health, safety and environmental regulatory compliance, there are also two very specific international standards on lignins: 1/ [ISO 9795:2023¹⁸](#) on *Lignins - Determination of inorganics content in kraft lignin, soda lignin and hydrolysis lignin* and 2/ [ISO 6350:2024¹⁹](#) on *Lignins - Determination of dry matter content - Oven-drying and freeze-drying methods*.

The PROSPALIGN consortium, based on these results and the understanding that the lignin valorisation market seems to be booming, recommends at this point of its research the creation of **an ISO standard to certify the characterization of lignin that can be used for the detection of bioactive molecules**. During our dissemination, communication and exploitation activities the last 16 months the project runs, we have come to a clear understanding of the complexity of the process as well as the factual lack of knowledge of the lignin producers themselves on the characterization of their lignin. There have been more than one occasions that lignin

¹² https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.C_.2021.013.01.0001.01.ENG&toc=OJ%3AC%3A2021%3A013%3ATOC

¹³ <https://cetaf.org/wp-content/uploads/CETAF-Code-of-Conduct-and-Best-Practice-for-Access-and-Benefit-Sharing-all-annexes-included.pdf>

¹⁴ ISO stands for the **International Organization for Standardization**. It is an independent, non-governmental international organization that develops and publishes standards to ensure the quality, safety, efficiency, and consistency of products, services, and systems across various industries. ISO has published over 23,000 international standards that cover a wide range of sectors, including technology, manufacturing, healthcare, and more. These standards help businesses and organizations in Nagoya improve their performance, manage risks effectively, and achieve sustainable growth. By adhering to ISO standards, companies can enhance their reputation, ensure regulatory compliance, and foster trust among customers and stakeholders.

¹⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/62085.html>

¹⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standards/popular/iso-14000-family>

¹⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/63787.html>

¹⁸ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/en/#iso:std:iso:9795:ed-1:v1:en>

¹⁹ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/en/#iso:std:iso:6350:ed-1:v1:en>

producers have offered the PROSPLIGN project their lignin samples for free in order to obtain more information on their samples' properties and qualities.

4 Concluding remarks

Following a thorough legislation and policy background research; a rigorous **internal consortium discussion**; and three designated **working sessions with our “sister project” [BRYOMOLECULES](#)** on which sort of recommendations to deliberate upon in this intermediate policy brief deliverable, the PROSPLIGN partners, with the integral guidance of our REA Project Officer, have reached a unanimous decision to focus on policy recommendations that surround the project's call topic of '**biodiversity**' and the Nagoya Protocol implementation which applies best to the project scope – lignin bioprospecting and valorisation.

The first two PROSPLIGN intermediate policy brief recommendations focus on knowledge transfer between the funding bodies and the beneficiaries for the better understanding and implementation of policy asks within the RIA funded projects framework. The third recommendation the PROSPLIGN partners have concluded in, suggests the creation and establishment of an entirely new ISO that will be linked to the characterization of lignin that can be used for the detection of bioactive molecules and can serve the entire lignin valorisation community with a standardised process to adhere to.

5 Annex

The annex lists the policies and EU regulations that match and fit the PROSPLIGN project scope and were part of the project's Description of Action.

The logic of this outline was to serve as a basis to investigate which of the policies and regulations the consortium and the Magfi team may make use of in light of the development of *deliverable D7.5 – Intermediate Policy Brief*, which was inserted and requested as an additional deliverable by the policy officer in the project's first amendment.

5.1 Policies and regulations mentioned in the PROSPLIGN project's Description of Action (DoA)

1/ GDPR regulations (T1.5)

[Regulation \(EU\) 2016/679](#): The general data protection regulation (GDPR) protects individuals when their data is being processed by the private sector and most of the public sector. The processing of data by the relevant authorities for law-enforcement purposes is subject to the data protection law enforcement directive (LED) instead. It allows individuals to better control their personal data. It also modernises and unifies rules, allowing businesses to reduce red tape and to benefit from greater consumer trust. It establishes a system of completely independent supervisory authorities in charge of monitoring and enforcing compliance. It is part of the European Union (EU) data protection reform, along with the data protection law enforcement directive and Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by the EU institutions, bodies, offices and agencies.

[Directive \(EU\) 2016/680](#): The decision authorised the signature (on 2 June 2016) of the agreement between the United States of America (US) and the European Union (EU) on the protection of personal information relating to the prevention, investigation, detection, and prosecution of criminal offences (the so-called 'Umbrella Agreement'). The agreement will enter into force only after the parties have notified each other that their respective internal procedures for entry into force have been completed (which, on the EU side, requires that the Council adopts a decision to conclude the agreement following consent by the European Parliament). The agreement aims to ensure that personal data is protected to a high standard when being transferred by law enforcement authorities (police and criminal justice authorities). It also aims to foster law enforcement cooperation between the EU and the EU countries, on the one hand, and the US on the other. It provides greater legal certainty and strengthens the rights of the individuals concerned by the transfer of their data.

2/ REACH regulation

[REACH Regulation \(EC\) No 1907/2006](#): applies to all chemical substances: manufactured, imported, sold, used on their own, in mixtures or in products. Companies must register, in a central database, all the chemicals they manufacture or import in quantities of 1 tonne or more per year. Companies must identify and manage any risks linked to the substances they manufacture and market in the EU. They must demonstrate how to use their products safely and inform users of any risk management measures they should take to ensure safe use throughout the supply chain. The legislation aims to replace the most hazardous substances with safer alternatives, where they are available.

3/ EU Bioeconomy Strategy

The [bioeconomy strategy](#) will accelerate the deployment of a sustainable European bioeconomy. It has 5 goals:

- ensure food and nutrition security
- manage natural resources sustainably
- reduce dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources
- limit and adapt to climate change
- strengthen European competitiveness and create jobs

The strategy contributes to the European Green Deal, as well as industrial, circular economy and clean energy innovation strategies. They all highlight the importance of a sustainable, circular bioeconomy to achieve their objectives.

4/ EU chemicals strategy for sustainability

The European Commission adopted its [Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability](#) on 14 October 2020. The strategy is part of the EU's zero pollution ambition – a key commitment of the European Green Deal – and aims to better protect citizens and the environment from harmful chemicals, and boost innovation by promoting the use of safer and more sustainable chemicals.

The Commission's strategy provides an action plan to:

- Ban the most harmful chemicals in consumer products – allowing those chemicals only where their use is essential.
- Pay attention to the cocktail effect of chemicals when assessing chemical risks.

- Phase out per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in the EU, unless their use is essential.
- Boost investment and innovative capacity for the production and use of chemicals that are safe and sustainable by design throughout their lifecycle.
- Promote the EU's supply and sustainability of critical chemicals.
- Establish a simpler “one substance, one assessment” process for assessing the risks and hazards of chemicals.
- Play a leading role globally by championing and promoting high chemical safety standards and not exporting chemicals banned in the EU.

5/ Sustainable Products Initiative (SPI)

This [initiative](#), which will revise the Ecodesign Directive and propose additional legislative measures as appropriate, aims to make products placed on the EU market more sustainable.

Consumers, the environment and the climate will benefit from products that are more durable, reusable, repairable, recyclable, and energy-efficient.

6/ Circular Economy Action Plan

The European Commission adopted the new [circular economy action plan](#) (CEAP) in March 2020. It is one of the main building blocks of the European Green Deal, Europe's new agenda for sustainable growth. The EU's transition to a circular economy will reduce pressure on natural resources and will create sustainable growth and jobs. It is also a prerequisite to achieve the EU's 2050 climate neutrality target and to halt biodiversity loss. The new action plan announces initiatives along the entire life cycle of products. It targets how products are designed, promotes circular economy processes, encourages sustainable consumption, and aims to ensure that waste is prevented, and the resources used are kept in the EU economy for as long as possible.

7/ The Nagoya Protocol and relevant national regulations (T6.2)

The [Nagoya Protocol](#) is a protocol to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), first signed by world leaders in 2010. The EU is a party to the CBD, together with 193 countries. The protocol aims to share out the benefits of using genetic resources in a fair and equitable way.

The protocol sets out mandatory rules on compliance for all parties, in order to monitor the use of genetic resources once they leave the provider country.

8/ UNEP SETAC Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organisations (United Nations Environment Programme, 2020) (T6.2)

The [guidelines](#) demystify the assessment of product life cycle social impacts and presents an effective framework representing the consensus of an international group of experts leading research in this field. The guidelines complement those for environmental life cycle assessment and life cycle costing, and by doing so contribute to the full assessment of goods and services within the context of sustainable development.

9/ EU Sustainable Finance Taxonomy Regulation

The [EU taxonomy](#) is a cornerstone of the EU's sustainable finance framework and an important market transparency tool. It helps direct investments to the economic activities most needed for the transition, in line with the European Green Deal objectives. The taxonomy is a classification system that defines criteria for economic activities that are aligned with a net zero trajectory by 2050 and the broader environmental goals other than climate.

5.2 Policies and regulations potentially applicable to the project as a whole and related to the identified Key Exploitable Results

The project must seek an ethical sourcing of biomass. The following policies and legislations can be relevant for the feedstock providers and applicable to each identified project KER.

1/ Regulation (EU) No 995/2010 on the obligations of operators who place timber and timber products on the market

[Regulation \(EU\) No 995/2010](#) prohibits illegally harvested timber from being placed on the EU market and sets out preconditions for the marketing of timber and timber products in the EU.

The regulation requires 'operators' who place timber products on the EU market for the first time to exercise 'due diligence' to ensure they supply products made of legally harvested timber. To this end, operators must use a due diligence system.

Operators may set up their own due diligence systems or use one created by a monitoring organisation.

Monitoring organisations are recognised as such by the European Commission. Their role is to assist operators comply with the requirements of the regulation.

To facilitate the traceability of timber products, all traders who buy and sell timber on the market must keep records of their suppliers and customers.

The regulation, which applies both to EU-harvested and imported timber, covers a wide range of timber products that are listed in the annex and are in accordance with the Union Customs Code.

The regulation considers timber/timber products to be legally harvested if they have a Forest Law Enforcement, Governance and Trade (FLEGT) licence (established with [Regulation \(EC\) No 2173/2005](#)), or a CITES permit ([Regulation \(EC\) No 338/97](#)).

2/ Convention on Biological Diversity

The [Convention on Biological Diversity \(CBD\)](#) is the international legal instrument for "the conservation of biological diversity, the sustainable use of its components and the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of the utilization of genetic resources" that has been ratified by 196 nations. Its overall objective is to encourage actions, which will lead to a sustainable future.

3/ Common agricultural policy (CAP) 2023-27

Launched in 1962, the EU's [common agricultural policy](#) (CAP) is a partnership between agriculture and society, and between Europe and its farmers. EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) is a partnership between agriculture and society, and between Europe and its farmers.

It aims to:

- support farmers and improve agricultural productivity, ensuring a stable supply of affordable food;
- safeguard European Union farmers to make a reasonable living;
- help tackle climate change and the sustainable management of natural resources;
- maintain rural areas and landscapes across the EU;
- keep the rural economy alive by promoting jobs in farming, agri-food industries and associated sectors.

The CAP is a common policy for all EU countries. It is managed and funded at European level from the resources of the EU's budget.

4/ EU Green Deal and Circular Economy Action Plan

EU chemicals policy and legislation, in particular REACH, encourage a shift to 'safe-by-design chemicals' through the progressive substitution of hazardous substances to better protect citizens and the environment.

The European Commission adopted the [new circular economy action plan \(CEAP\)](#) in March 2020. It is one of the main building blocks of the [European Green Deal](#), Europe's new agenda for sustainable growth. The EU's transition to a circular economy will reduce pressure on natural resources and will create sustainable growth and jobs. It is also a prerequisite to achieve the EU's 2050 climate neutrality target and to halt biodiversity loss.

The new action plan announces initiatives along the entire life cycle of products. It targets how products are designed, promotes circular economy processes, encourages sustainable consumption, and aims to ensure that waste is prevented and the resources used are kept in the EU economy for as long as possible.

5/ Commission Regulation (EU) 2023/1545

[Commission Regulation \(EU\) 2023/1545](#) is amending Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards labelling of fragrance allergens in cosmetic products.

6/ Directive 1999/31/EC

[Directive 1999/31/EC](#) aims to prevent, or reduce as much as possible, any negative impact from landfill on surface water, groundwater, soil, air or human health. It does so by introducing stringent technical requirements.

7/ Directive 2001/83/EC

[Directive 2001/83/EC](#) declares that all medicines offered for sale in the EU must have prior authorisation from either a national authority or the European Medicines Agency. To receive the authorisation, manufacturers must provide a range of detailed therapeutic information about the product, including any possible side-effects. Authorisation may be refused if a medicine's risk-benefit ratio is not considered favourable or its therapeutic effect is insufficiently substantiated. Pharmacovigilance systems: systems set in place to monitor the effects of medicines and, in particular, to identify and assess adverse reactions.

8/ Directive 2001/95/EC

[Directive 2001/95/EC](#) states that products placed on the EU market must be safe. They must bear information enabling them to be traced, such as the manufacturer's identity and a product reference. Where necessary for safe use, products must be accompanied by warnings and information about any inherent risks. A product is considered safe if it meets specific national requirements or EU standards.

9/ Directive 96/9/EC

[Directive 96/9/EC](#) applies to databases, irrespective of their form (e.g. electronic (online) or non-electronic (offline)); does not apply to the software used in the making or operation of the database or to the works and materials it contains copyright protection for the intellectual creation involved in the selection and arrangement of materials; sui generis* protection for a substantial investment (financial and in terms of human resources, effort and energy) in obtaining, verifying or presenting the contents of a database.

10/ Directive 98/44/EC

[Directive 98/44/EC](#) on the Legal Protection of Biotechnological Inventions: Inventions which concern a product consisting of, or containing, biological material* or a process for the production of such biological material may be patented if they are new, involve an inventive step and can be applied industrially.

11/ Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009

[Regulation \(EC\) No 1223/2009](#) states that all cosmetic products need a safety report before they can be placed on the market.

There must be a ‘responsible person’ for each product. All cosmetic products must be registered only once, in the EU’s Cosmetic Products Notification Portal. Packaging must include a range of information, including the name and the address of the responsible person, the contents, precautions for use and the list of ingredients. The regulation sets out rules for the use of nanomaterials. It also includes lists of substances which are prohibited, restricted or authorised for use in cosmetics. Labelling information on cosmetic products must include a list of ingredients; the ingredients are to be expressed using the common ingredient names set out in a glossary to be compiled and updated by the European Commission. In addition, since in some cases it is difficult to distinguish between medical devices and cosmetic products, Article 119 of Regulation (EU) 2017/745 amends Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 by making it possible to take an EU-wide decision on the regulatory status of a product. As of 26 May 2021, the Commission may, at the request of a Member State or on its own initiative, decide whether or not a specific product or group of products falls within the definition of a ‘cosmetic product’.

12/ Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008

[Regulation \(EC\) No 1272/2008](#) lays down uniform requirements for the classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of chemical substances and mixtures according to the United Nations’ globally harmonised system (GHS). It requires companies to classify, label and package hazardous chemicals appropriately before placing them on the market.

13/ Regulation (EC) No 66/2010

[Regulation \(EC\) No 66/2010](#) outlines how the EU Ecolabel may be awarded to products and services which have a lower environmental impact than other products in the same group. The label criteria were devised using scientific data on the whole of a product's life cycle, from product development to disposal. The label may be awarded to all goods or services distributed, consumed or used on the EU market whether in return for payment or free of charge, on condition that the ecological criteria have been clearly established. It does not apply to medicinal products for human or veterinary use, or to medical devices. The label cannot be awarded to products containing substances classified by Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 as toxic, hazardous to the environment, carcinogenic or mutagenic, or substances subject to the regulatory framework for the management of chemicals.

14/ Regulation (EC) No 726/2004

[Regulation \(EC\) No 726/2004](#) introduces a centralised authorisation procedure for medicinal products in addition to existing national systems. This centralised procedure is compulsory for: products containing any new substance to treat cancer. The procedure is optional where: a new active substance is involved, or an innovation is of interest at EU level.

15/ Regulation (EU) 2018/1807

[Regulation \(EU\) 2018/1807](#) aims to ensure that electronic data, apart from personal data, can be processed freely throughout the EU.

16/ Regulation (EU) No 1257/2012

[Regulation \(EU\) No 1257/2012](#) is on the Unitary Patent. The unitary patent is a legal title that provides uniform protection across all participating EU member countries on a one-stop-shop basis, providing huge cost advantages and reducing administrative burden.

17/ Regulation (EU) No 536/2014

[Regulation \(EU\) No 536/2014](#) is outlining legal criteria for clinical trials on medicinal products for human use.

18/ Regulation (EU) No 655/2013

[Regulation \(EU\) No 655/2013](#) shall apply to claims in the form of texts, names, trademarks, pictures and figurative or other signs that convey explicitly or implicitly product characteristics or functions in the labelling, the making available on the market and advertising of cosmetic products. It shall apply to any claim, irrespective of the medium or type of marketing tool used, the product functions claimed, and the target audience.